

EFFECT OF PLAYING FLASHCARDS ON FINE MOTOR DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN AT TK-RA HIDAYATUSSHIBYAN CINERE

Betty^{1*}, Osty Histry Kapahang¹, Katmini¹, Femmy Aprilia tanjung¹

¹Nursing Study Program, STIKes Widya Dharma Husada, Tangerang, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received July 01, 2025

Revised July 20, 2025

Accepted July 31, 2025

Keywords:

Flashcard

Motorik Halus

Preschool

ABSTRACT

Fine motor development is a crucial aspect of early childhood growth. Data shows that 27.5% of toddlers in Indonesia experience fine motor developmental disorders. One method of stimulation that can be used is flashcard play. This study aimed to determine the effect of playing flashcards on fine motor development in preschool children at TK RA Hidayatusshibyan Cinere. The research used a pre-experimental one-group pretest-posttest design with a sample of 40 children selected by total sampling. The intervention lasted for three weeks. Data were collected through fine motor observation sheets and analyzed using the Wilcoxon test. The results showed a significant difference between pretest and posttest scores with a p-value of 0.000. Children showed improvements, with 26 (65.0%) categorized as 'good' and 14 (35.0%) as 'very good'.

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Corresponding Author:

Betty

Nursing Study Program, STIKes Widya Dharma Husada, Tangerang, Indonesia

Email: Betchy_cew@ymail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) reported that globally, 149.2 million children aged 4–6 years experienced developmental disorders in 2020. The prevalence of developmental disorders is highest among children living in low- and middle-income countries, accounting for 95%. In Indonesia, the prevalence of developmental delays in children under the age of five was reported by WHO in 2018 at 7,512.6 per 100,000 population (7.51%) (WHO, 2021). According to the 2018 Indonesian Child Development Index Survey, 90.04% of children had normal development, which means that 9.6% of children aged 36–59 months experienced developmental delays. West Java province contributed to a prevalence of 8.3% among toddlers aged 36–59 months who experienced developmental delays (Ministry of Health, 2019). National data on the incidence of growth and developmental disorders in toddlers, particularly fine motor developmental delays, showed that 27.5% or approximately 3 million children were affected. According to Indonesia's Ministry of Health, in 2014, between 13% and 18% of children under five years old experienced growth and developmental abnormalities (Wardani, 2021).

Indonesia's 2018 Health Profile states that early childhood (ages 2–5) accounted for 23.7 million individuals or 10.4% of the national population. Data on child development indicates that 65.8% of children

had good cognitive development, while approximately 0.4 million children (16%) suffered from fine and gross motor impairments, reduced creativity and intelligence, and delayed speech. Growth and developmental disorders among children in Indonesia reached 35.7%, classifying it as a major public health issue based on WHO criteria, which consider a rate above 30% as high (Ministry of Health, 2020).

In general, the domains of child development include gross motor skills, fine motor skills, language/speech, and personal-social or self-care skills. About 5% to 10% of Indonesian children experience developmental delays. Although the exact incidence rate of global developmental delays is not clearly known, it is estimated that around 1–3% of children under the age of five experience such delays (Kasim et al., 2021). Fine motor skills involve the coordination of small muscles, particularly those of the hands and fingers, along with eye-hand coordination. The development of fine motor skills serves as a foundation for enhancing hand dexterity, and the progress in this area corresponds to the maturation of a child's muscular and nervous systems (Izzah et al., 2021). Data show that the incidence of developmental delays among toddlers, especially in fine motor development, remains high at 27.5% or approximately 3 million children (Yanti, 2020). One of the influential factors in the development of preschool children is play. Play is considered the most valuable activity, as it enables children to engage their sensory and motor functions. For example, playing with sand can refine fine motor skills by training finger muscle movements, tactile nerves, and wrist coordination—important for developing early writing abilities in preschoolers (Yuniati, 2018).

Makmun Khairani explained that fine motor development refers to the growth of hand muscles in children, allowing them to perform coordinated tasks such as crumpling paper, holding objects, writing, tearing paper, or other activities requiring manual dexterity. Stimulating the development of fine motor skills is essential, as these movements support various daily activities. If a child is unable to properly develop their fine motor skills, they may struggle with tasks requiring hand coordination, such as dressing themselves or tying their shoes.

Hurlock identified several reasons why fine motor development is important for a child's overall development: First, motor skills allow children to entertain themselves and experience joy, such as through playing with dolls or throwing and catching balls. Second, motor development enables children to transition from helplessness in the early months of life to independence, as they learn to move and act on their own, boosting self-confidence. Third, motor skills facilitate school adjustment; preschool and early elementary-age children can be taught to draw, paint, participate in drills, and prepare for writing (Fauziddin, 2018).

Flashcards are a form of visual learning media consisting of picture cards shown quickly to children. According to Mansyur (2018), flashcards were introduced by Glenn Doman, a brain surgeon from Philadelphia, Pennsylvania. These cards, which include pictures and words, are shown rapidly to children while the words are read aloud. According to Ratnawati in Rahman et al. (2017), flashcards can stimulate children to recognize numbers more quickly, increase their interest in mastering numerical concepts, and enhance intelligence and memory. Therefore, the use of flashcards can help children learn early math concepts such as numbers and basic geometric shapes, as well as objects resembling these shapes. Based on this background, the authors reviewed literature on the use of flashcards to introduce early mathematics to young children (Azhima et al., 2021).

The use of educational media facilitates more effective and efficient teaching and message delivery. According to Nurmayah Ida et al. (2016), "In general, the benefit of media in the learning process is to ease interaction between teachers and students, thereby making learning activities more effective and efficient." By using media in the teaching process, teachers can deliver learning material more easily. One such medium is flashcards.

2. METHOD

This study is a quantitative research employing an experimental method. The design used is a pre-experimental design. Specifically, the type of pre-experimental design applied in this study is the One Group Pretest-Posttest Design. In this design, tests were conducted twice: before and after the intervention. The

observation conducted prior to the intervention is referred to as the pre-intervention, followed by the administration of the treatment or intervention, and then the observation conducted afterward is referred to as the post-intervention (Sugiyono, 2014). The study was conducted at TK RA Hidayatusshibyan Cinere, located at Jl. Masjid I No. 30, Cinere, Depok City. The research took place in December 2024. The population in this study consisted of all students at TK RA Hidayatusshibyan Cinere. The sampling technique used was total sampling, involving 40 participants.

Instruments and Data Collection Methods:

1. Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) Sheet for Playing Flashcards
2. Fine Motor Skills Observation Sheet
3. Informed Consent Form

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study discusses the effect of playing flashcards on fine motor development in preschool-aged children at TK-RA Hidayatusshibyan Cinere, conducted in December 2024, with a total of 40 respondents.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution Based on the Age of Preschool Children at TK RA Hidayatusshibyan Cinere

Age	Frequency	Percentage
5 Years	28	70.0%
6 Years	12	30.0%
Total	40	100%

Based on Table 1, among the 40 respondents, 28 (70.0%) were 5 years old, and 12 (30.0%) were 6 years old.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution Based on Gender of Preschool Children at TK RA Hidayatusshibyan Cinere

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	14	35.0%
Female	26	65.0%
Total	40	100%

Based on Table 2, of the 40 respondents, 14 (35.0%) were male and 26 (65.0%) were female.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Respondents Based on Fine Motor Development Before (Pretest) Playing Flashcards

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Poor	7	15.5%
Fair	23	57.5%
Good	10	25.0%
Excellent	0	0.0%
Total	40	100%

Table 4: Frequency Distribution Based on Fine Motor Development After (Posttest) Playing Flashcards

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Poor	0	0.0%
Fair	0	0.0%
Good	26	65.0%
Excellent	14	35.0%
Total	40	100%

Based on Table 4, the distribution of fine motor development after the flashcard intervention showed that 0% of respondents were in the poor or fair categories. A total of 26 children (65.0%) were categorized as good, and 14 children (35.0%) were categorized as excellent.

Table 5: Comparison of Fine Motor Development Before (Pretest) and After (Posttest) Playing Flashcards

Pre-test	Post-test
Poor (17.5%)	Poor (0%)
Fair (57.5%)	Fair (0%)
Good (25.0%)	Good (65.0%)
Excellent (0%)	Excellent (35.0%)

Based on Table 5, the comparison between pretest and posttest results shows notable improvement: the percentage in the poor category decreased from 17.5% to 0%, and the fair category from 57.5% to 0%. Meanwhile, the good category increased from 25.0% to 65.0%, and the excellent category increased from 0% to 35.0%.

Table 6: Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Results for the Effect of Playing Flashcards on Fine Motor Development in Preschool Children

Comparison	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Negative Ranks	0	0.00	0.00		
Positive Ranks	39	20.00	780.00	-5.500	0.000
Ties	1				
Total	40				

To determine whether the hypothesis is accepted or rejected, the p-value is compared to a significance level of 5% (0.05). If the p-value is greater than 0.05, the hypothesis is rejected; if it is less than 0.05, the hypothesis is accepted. Based on Table 6, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test results showed a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, indicating a significant difference in fine motor development before and after the flashcard intervention. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted (H_a).

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the study on the effect of playing flashcards on the fine motor development of preschool children at TK RA Hidayatusshibyan Cinere with a total of 40 respondents, the following conclusions were drawn:

- a. Among the 40 respondents, 26 (65.0%) were female.
- b. Prior to the flashcard intervention (pretest), 10 respondents (25.0%) showed good fine motor development.
- c. After the flashcard intervention (posttest), 14 respondents (35.0%) showed excellent fine motor development.
- d. The effect of playing flashcards on fine motor development was evident from the comparison between pretest and posttest results, which showed changes in distribution: the percentage in the poor category decreased from 17.5% to 0%, in the fair category from 57.5% to 0%, in the good category increased from 25.0% to 65.0%, and in the excellent category increased from 0% to 35.0%. The statistical analysis using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test yielded a p-value of 0.000, indicating a significant effect of flashcard play on the improvement of fine motor development.

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